

FACEBOOK CONTENT CREATION AND YOUTH UNEMPLOYMENT IN RURAL SOUTH AFRICA

Author: Nhlawulo Arnold Baburi*

Affiliation: University of Limpopo

Address; C/O R71 Tzaneen Road and University Street, Mankweng Township, Polokwane, Limpopo Province, South Africa

Cell: + 2765940 2655

Gmail: arnoldbaburi1@gmail.com

Co-author: Dr. Wonder Juniper

Affiliation: University of Limpopo

Address: C/O R71 Tzaneen Road and University Street, Mankweng Township, Polokwane, Limpopo Province, South Africa

Cell: +27 61 549 5704

Email: wonder.juniper@ul.ac.za

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Note: This journal article is based on research conducted for the author's Master of Arts dissertation in Media Studies, titled Facebook Usage and Youth Involvement in the Content Creation Industry. The study explored how Facebook usage and youth participation in content creation could serve as a potential strategy for addressing poverty and unemployment in the Capricorn District

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the dynamics of Facebook content creation as a strategy for addressing youth unemployment in the rural Capricorn district of the Limpopo province, South Africa. Building upon existing research, the study addressed a gap in understanding the potential of social media content creation to address poverty and unemployment among youth in rural areas. The study focused on a sample of 10 video content creators, between the ages of 18 and 34, with Facebook accounts and 5,000+ followers, drawn from the youth population in the Capricorn district. Employing the Uses and Gratification Theory, the study used a qualitative approach with semi-structured interviews conducted via Facebook Conference Room and WhatsApp, and thematic analysis with NVivo software analyses the data. The findings revealed that Facebook content creation provides an economic empowerment opportunity for youth in the Capricorn district; however, youth content creators face challenges such as inconsistency, technical issues, and limited resources. In conclusion, the study found that Facebook content creation has the potential to be a viable income-generating activity for young people in rural areas, recommending support and resources from the Capricorn District Municipality and National Youth Development Agency (NYDA) to foster growth and development. Limitations include difficulties in finding targeted participants and a smaller-than-targeted sample size of content creators with 10,000+ followers. Future research should investigate the role of social media entrepreneurship in the creator economy as a strategy to address youth unemployment in post-COVID-19 South Africa, aligning with Agenda 2030's goals.

Keywords: content creation, content creator, Facebook, social media, youth

1.1 INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

Youth unemployment remains a pressing global concern, with approximately 67.6 million young people unemployed worldwide in 2020, predominantly in low-income countries with informal economies (Mercy Corps, 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic exacerbated this issue, leading to an increased global youth unemployment rate to 14.9% (Statistics SA, 2022). In South Africa, the youth unemployment rate is alarmingly high, reaching 43.4% among those aged 15 to 34 in the third quarter of 2023 (Naidu, 2023). The Capricorn district in the Limpopo province faces an even more difficult situation, with a youth unemployment rate of 47.4%, surpassing the national average (Statistics SA, 2024). Conversely, the global digital content creation industry has experienced significant growth, valued at USD 25.6 billion in 2022, with an estimated compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 13.5% from 2023 to 2030 (Grand View Research, 2023). This growth is accompanied by a substantial increase in content creators worldwide, with over 200 million individuals engaged in content creation (Howarth, 2024). In South Africa, the content creation space is thriving, with video content dominating platforms like TikTok and Instagram (McInnes, 2024). Despite the growth of the digital content creation industry, there is a lack of research into the specific context of youth involvement in content creation in South Africa, particularly in rural areas like the Capricorn district. This study aimed to explore the dynamics of Facebook content creation as a strategy for addressing unemployment among youth in the rural Capricorn district. Specifically, it sought to answer the research question: "How do the dynamics of Facebook content creation function as a strategy for addressing youth unemployment in the rural Capricorn district?" This study focused on youth aged 18 to -34 with a verified Facebook account and 10,000+ followers, aiming to contribute to the existing body of knowledge on youth entrepreneurship and social media empowerment.

1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

The rise of social media has given birth to a new kind of job – content creation – which has become a dream career for many young people (Darma, 2023). Platforms like Facebook, Instagram, and TikTok have provided career opportunities for content creators and new marketing options for companies (Rwanda, 2018). However, despite being spearheads of ICT usage, particularly in new media, the youth suffer from

unemployment and underemployment, and although they are the biggest users of these platforms, they are often used more for socialisation than for harnessing their full potential to address these challenges (Rwanda, 2018). Notably, there is a dearth of research on rural social media usage in Africa, particularly in South Africa, creating a scholarly lacuna that this study aimed to address. The Capricorn district, with a youth unemployment rate of 47.4% (Statistics SA, 2024), exceeding the national average, presents a pressing case for exploring innovative strategies to address this issue. The content creation industry has the potential to address this issue, but limited studies have explored the dynamics of social media usage on youth participation in this industry. The problem addressed in this study was that limited research explored the potential impact of Facebook usage on youth participation and content creation activities in addressing poverty and unemployment in rural areas, specifically the Capricorn district. This gap is significant, especially considering the high youth unemployment rates in rural areas, highlighting the need for research on leveraging social media for economic empowerment. Therefore, this study aimed to explore the dynamics of Facebook content creation as a strategy for reducing poverty and unemployment, providing insights into how social media could be leveraged to promote entrepreneurship, self-employment, and skills development among young people in rural areas.

1.3 PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

1.3.1 Aim

The study aimed to explore the dynamics of Facebook content creation as a strategy for addressing unemployment among youth in the rural Capricorn district.

1.3.2 Objective

- To critically analyse the processes, motivations, and challenges associated with youth utilising Facebook content creation as a viable economic strategy within the rural Capricorn district.

1.4 RESEARCH QUESTION

- How do the dynamics of Facebook content creation function as a strategy for addressing youth unemployment in the rural Capricorn district?

1.5 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study addressed a critical knowledge gap in understanding the dynamics of Facebook content creation as a strategy for addressing youth unemployment in rural South Africa. By exploring the processes, motivations, and challenges associated with youth utilising Facebook content creation as a viable economic strategy, this research provides new insights into the potential of Facebook content creation to address poverty and unemployment in rural areas like the Capricorn district. The findings of this study had several significant implications. Facebook content creation can generate income and lead to careers, jobs, or entrepreneurial ventures, highlighting its potential to address unemployment in rural South Africa. This study contributes to the limited research on rural social media usage in South Africa, providing context-specific insights into the dynamics of Facebook content creation and youth unemployment in the Capricorn district. The study's findings can inform the development of effective policies and programmes addressing youth unemployment and poverty in rural areas, aligning with the objectives of the NYDA Act, Act No. 54 of 2008 (South Africa, 2009). The study's insights can support the development of programmes and initiatives that promote youth empowerment and address challenges facing young people in rural South Africa.

1.6 LITERATURE REVIEW

1.6.1 Content creation and youth involvement

Content creators are defined as individuals who consistently produce and share content on digital platforms, often specialising in specific domains such as fashion, travel, or music (Sukhraj, 2024; Bhargava, 2022; Valsesia, Proserpio, & Nunes, 2020). According to Bhargava (2022), content creators are digitally savvy individuals who create content around their interests, hobbies, and experiences, and distribute and monetise it on digital platforms. Research findings suggest that content creators share content on social media platforms to earn money, often accumulating fortunes by promoting businesses and brands (Etukudo, 2024). Content creation plays a crucial role in personal branding, enabling individuals to showcase their talents and services (Gynn, 2022). However, content creators often face criticism and challenges, particularly in the beginning stages of their journey (Sidewalker Daily, 2024). To overcome these challenges, content creators can focus on being true to themselves,

listening to their intuition, and processing criticism calmly and professionally (Sidewalker Daily, 2024).

Many content creators also struggle with consistency due to busy schedules, which can make it challenging to maintain a strong online presence (Hersh, 2020). The motivations behind content creation vary, with some creators driven by the desire to gain followers (El Sanyoura & Anderson, 2022), generate engagement (Geysler, 2022), or monetise content (Bhargava, 2022). These findings highlight the complexity of the creator-platform relationship and the need for supportive platforms. In terms of youth involvement in content creation, research suggests that young people are highly active on social media platforms and have a strong desire to become content creators (Sirmayanti et al., 2022). Platforms like TikTok, Snapchat, and Instagram are particularly popular among Gen Z users, who use them to create and consume content (Buleen, 2023).

The findings also suggest that youth involvement in content creation is characterised by diverse motivations, strategic platform use, and a desire for creativity and empowerment. Overall, the literature suggests that content creation offers young people opportunities for self-expression, creativity, and entrepreneurship. What it means to youth involvement in the content creation industry is that young people have the potential to leverage digital platforms to build their personal brands, showcase their talents, and earn money.

Studies suggest that young people are drawn to content creation as a means of generating income, particularly in the face of economic uncertainty (Howarth, 2023; Wilson, 2024). This finding is supported by research that highlights the potential for content creation to provide self-employment opportunities and enable youths to earn a living through online entrepreneurship (Nwankwor et al., 2024). Furthermore, content creation can be a valuable career pathway, offering opportunities for skill development and career advancement (Lee, 2020). However, research also notes that many content creators face challenges, including limited resources and intense competition (Vahey, 2023; Törhönen, Sjöblom & Hamari, 2018). Despite these challenges, Generation Z has a strong desire to become content creators, indicating a positive attitude towards content creation (Sirmayanti et al., 2022). This enthusiasm for content creation is likely driven by the creative freedom and personal fulfilment it offers, as well

as the potential for financial gain. The findings have implications for our understanding of the youth's perceptions of content creation. They suggest that young people view content creation as a viable and attractive career option, valuing its potential for skills development, creative freedom, and income generation. However, they also highlight the need for supportive platforms and resources to help young content creators navigate the industry's challenges.

Overall, the findings suggest that young people are drawn to the industry's potential for financial rewards, creative expression, and personal fulfilment. Studies suggest that the youth use Facebook for multiple objectives, including social interaction, information-seeking, career development, and self-expression (López & Paniagua, 2019; Alim & AlShourbaji, 2020; Sundani, 2019). These findings are supported by Fu, Wu, and Cho's (2017) study, which highlighted Facebook's role as a prominent platform for content sharing. Research on Facebook usage patterns reveals peak activity times and optimal posting days, with weekdays and morning hours tending to be most effective for engagement (Keutelian, 2024; Macready, 2024). These findings are consistent with those of the study conducted by Greenwood, Perrin, and Duggan (2016), which showed that young people access Facebook eight times daily. However, studies on gender differences in Facebook usage present mixed results.

While some research suggests that females spend more time on Facebook than males (Biernatowska, Balcerowska, & Bereznowski, 2017; Memon, Jamali, & Pathan, 2017), others found no significant difference in Facebook usage between male and female respondents (Jordaan & Ndhlovu, 2017). These opposing findings highlight the need for further research on gender differences in Facebook usage. The literature also notes that Facebook usage is influenced by factors such as age, income, and education level (Lutz, 2022), which is consistent with the findings of Thiers' (2022) study on social disconnection and segregation by income in US communities on Facebook. The findings have implications for understanding Facebook usage among the youth. They suggest that Facebook is an integral part of youths' online lives, serving multiple purposes, including social interaction, entertainment, knowledge sharing, and self-expression. Understanding these usage patterns and demographics can help policymakers, marketers, and content creators develop targeted strategies to engage with youth on Facebook.

1.6.2 Literature gap

There is a contextual gap in this thematic literature review, which pertains to the lack of research specifically focusing on the dynamics of Facebook content creation as a strategy for addressing youth unemployment in rural South Africa, particularly in areas like the Capricorn district. While existing research provides insights into content creation and youth unemployment globally, including in South Africa, there is a need for research exploring these dynamics within the unique context of rural South Africa. By conducting a study in the Capricorn district, the research aimed to address this contextual gap and provide localised insights into the dynamics of Facebook content creation and its potential to address youth unemployment in rural areas. A contextual gap refers to the absence of research in specific contexts, such as specific populations, geographic areas, or periods, despite an existing body of research on the topic (Al-Saraf & Rautenbach, 2022).

1.6.3 Uses and Gratifications Theory

This study was underpinned by the Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT). The UGT, developed by Blumler and Katz in 1974, posits that individuals actively select and use media to fulfil specific needs and desires, rather than being passive recipients of media content (Blumler & Katz, 1974). The UGT was relevant to this study as it explained why youth in the Capricorn district use Facebook for content creation. According to the UGT, media use is goal-directed, and individuals choose media that satisfy their needs, such as entertainment, information, or social interaction (Ruggiero, 2000). In this context, the youth use Facebook to create content, build their personal brand, and potentially earn income, thereby fulfilling their needs for creativity, self-expression, and financial gain. The UGT has been applied in various studies on social media use and content creation. For instance, research has shown that individuals use social media platforms like Facebook to gratify their needs for social interaction, entertainment, and self-promotion (Whiting & Williams, 2013). Similarly, this study explored how the youth in the Capricorn district use Facebook to gratify their needs for content creation, personal branding, and economic empowerment. The UGT's core assumptions, as outlined by Katz, Blumler, and Gurevitch (1974), are:

1. Media use is goal-directed.
2. Audiences play an active role in the media they consume.
3. Media competes with other sources to fulfil needs.

In this study, the UGT helps explain why youth in the Capricorn district are motivated to create content on Facebook, and how they use the platform to fulfil their needs and desires.

1.7 METHODOLOGY

This study adopted an interpretive philosophical framework to investigate the perceptions, knowledge, and experiences of youth in the Capricorn district regarding Facebook content creation and its potential to address youth unemployment. According to Henning, Van Rensburg and Smit (2004), knowledge is constructed through observable phenomena and people's intentions, beliefs, values, reasons, meaning making, and self-understanding. The interpretive paradigm aims to "understand the subjective world of human experience" (Cohen, Manion & Morrison, 2018). The study employed a qualitative research approach, which is an inquiry that aims to gain an in-depth understanding of human behaviour and the reasons that govern such behaviour (Shava & Nkengbeza, 2019). This approach was appropriate for this study as it sought to understand youths' engagement with Facebook content creation and its implications for youth unemployment, examining their perceptions, knowledge, and experiences of the industry. A case study design was adopted, allowing for a comprehensive exploration of the research topic and providing an in-depth understanding of contextual factors (Coombs, 2022; Kapoor, 2022).

The study population consisted of youth aged 18 to 34 years, selected using purposive sampling techniques. Data saturation determined the sample size, with a total of 10 participants meeting the criteria: verified Facebook accounts, 10,000+ followers, and active video content creation. Semi-structured and in-depth interviews were conducted via Facebook Conference Room and WhatsApp voice note chat, gathering rich, detailed data about participants' perceptions, experiences, and knowledge (Ruslin et al., 2022; Rutledge & Hogg, 2020). Data was collected from 20/09/24 to 13/03/25. Following Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-phase process, thematic analysis was used to analyse the data, facilitated by NVivo qualitative data analysis software. This study followed Guba's (1981) four quality criteria for qualitative studies, as updated by

Megheirkouni and Moir (2023), namely credibility, dependability, transferability, and confirmability, to ensure the trustworthiness and rigour of the research findings. These criteria were met through transparent methodology, systematic documentation, detailed contextual description, and reflexive practices to minimise researcher bias (Megheirkouni & Moir, 2023).

1.8 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The study adhered to ethical research principles by obtaining permission from the University of Limpopo Turfloop Research Ethics Committee. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring they were fully aware of the study's benefits, risks, and procedures. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained by not disclosing participants' real names and using the information solely for research purposes. Furthermore, participants were assured of their right to voluntary participation, allowing them to withdraw at any time without obligation.

1.8.1 Ethical Approval Statement (FULL DETAILS)

*Ethical approval for this study was granted by the Turfloop Research Ethics Committee (TREC) of the University of Limpopo. The study was approved under reference number **TREC/1593/2024: PG** on **19 September 2024**. A copy of the ethical clearance certificate has been included at the end of this document, immediately following the references.*

1.9 PRESENTATION OF RESULTS AND FINDINGS

1.9.1 Data presentation

The study found that several participants generated income through Facebook, either through direct monetisation, indirect monetisation, or both, while a few do not generate income at all. Participants mentioned financial gain as a motivator, including earning money through Facebook monetisation options (Participants 2, 4, 5, 7, 8, and 10). The study found that participants saw content creation as a viable career path, opening opportunities for collaborations, business ventures, and employment. Participants believed that content creation can empower individuals, especially the youth, to fight poverty and unemployment (Participants 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10). Many participants mentioned posting content daily or regularly (Participants 1, 2, 7, 8, and

9). Consistency was a significant challenge for some participants, who struggled with time constraints, lack of content, and difficulty in maintaining a consistent posting schedule (Participants 4, 5, 6, and 7). Participants reported varying levels of Facebook usage, ranging from less than an hour (Participant 7) to over 10 hours (Participant 1) per day. All participants emphasised Facebook's importance as a platform for sharing content, reaching a large audience, and building a community. Most participants used Professional Mode accounts, citing benefits like convenient features and analytics. A few used Standard Accounts, and a few used Facebook Pages, and only one had a verified account. Participants mentioned facing technical challenges such as network issues, data limitations, and inadequate equipment (Participants 1, 3, 4, 7, 8, 9, and 10).

1.10 DISCUSSION AND INTERPRETATION OF FINDINGS

Theme 1: Economic empowerment

1.10.1 Participants were asked to describe their experiences with Facebook monetisation, including the strategies they used to generate income and the challenges they faced in leveraging the platform for financial gain.

Sub-theme 1.1: Monetisation and income

Monetisation is the process of turning assets, skills, or resources into profit-generating opportunities, whereas income represents the actual earnings derived from these sources. Facebook monetisation involves utilising the platform to generate revenue through methods such as video ads, subscription-based models, and partnering with brands to promote their products or services. Some participants, like Participants 1 and 10, earned money directly through Facebook monetisation options, while others generated income indirectly by promoting businesses or advertising for others. In line with the UGT, participants' use of Facebook for monetisation and income generation reflected their active selection of media to fulfil financial goals. The study found that several participants generated income through Facebook, either through direct monetisation, indirect monetisation, or both, while a few did not generate income at all. The findings align with Bhargava's (2022) definition of content creators as individuals who create and monetise content on digital platforms. The findings highlight the potential of Facebook as a platform for youth involvement in the global content

creation industry in the Capricorn district, offering a viable means of addressing poverty and unemployment among young people.

1.10.2 The participants were asked to tell what motivates them to engage in content creation.

Sub-theme 1.2: Financial gain and monetisation

Financial gain and monetisation refer to the process of generating revenue or income through various means, such as converting assets, data, or online content into profitable sources, ultimately leading to financial benefits and increased earnings. Several participants mentioned financial gain as a motivator, including earning money through Facebook monetisation options (Participants 2, 4, 5, 7, 8, and 10). Participant 5 stated that financial gain was their primary motivation by stating, "Honestly, my primary motivation is financial gain, as money is essential for survival." Participant 10 noted that their goals shifted after becoming aware of monetisation opportunities, "Now that I'm aware of the monetisation opportunities, my goals have shifted. I now have two objectives: to share my talent and to earn money through social media and content creation." The study found that several participants mentioned financial gain as a motivator for content creation, with some citing Facebook's monetisation options as a key driver. The trend of prioritising financial gain as a motivator for content creation is supported by Howarth's (2023) observation that individuals are seeking alternative income sources due to an impending financial crisis, and Wilson's (2024) note that content creation has emerged as a viable alternative for young people amidst economic uncertainty. In line with the UGT, participants' use of Facebook for financial gain reflected on their active selection of media to fulfil financial goals, aligning with the theory's assumption that "media use is perceived to be goal-directed" (Blumler & Katz, 1974). Content creation emerges as a vital strategy for addressing the high youth unemployment rate in South Africa, particularly in the Capricorn district, by providing alternative income sources and opportunities for financial gain.

1.10.3 Participants were asked to explain how they perceived the value and importance of content creation in terms of personal fulfilment and career opportunities.

Sub-theme 1.3: Career opportunities and advancement

Content creation offers diverse career opportunities, ranging from entry-level roles like social media content creator to specialised positions like content strategist or marketing manager. Many participants believed that content creation can open up career opportunities, such as collaborations, business ventures, and employment (Participants 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, and 7). Participant 3 stated, "I recall being told that education is the key to success. However, I've come to realise that content creation can also be a pathway to success," while Participant 7 noted that "From a career perspective, content creation has provided me with valuable experience in digital marketing and social media management." Participants 4 and 8 expressed differing views on content creation as a career, with Participant 4 seeing it as a side hustle and Participant 8 believing it does not directly contribute to their career as an information studies student. The study found that participants saw content creation as a viable career path, opening opportunities for collaborations, business ventures, and employment. In line with the UGT, participants' pursuit of career opportunities through content creation reflected their active selection of media to fulfil career goals, aligning with the theory's assumption that "media use is perceived to be goal-directed" (Blumler & Katz, 1974). This is supported by Lee (2020), who suggests that content creation can be a valuable career pathway, providing opportunities for skills development and career advancement. Leveraging content creation can be a vital strategy for unlocking career opportunities and addressing youth unemployment.

1.10.4 The study sought to understand how content creators' perceptions and attitudes shape their involvement in content creation, particularly their views on its potential as a tool for combating poverty and unemployment among young people.

Sub-theme 1.4: Empowerment and financial gain

Empowerment and financial gain through content creation is a form of economic empowerment that enables individuals, especially the youth, to earn a living, combat poverty and unemployment, and achieve financial stability through creating and monetising online content. Participants believed that content creation can empower individuals, especially the youth, to fight poverty and unemployment (Participants 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10). Participant 1 noted, "Content creation can be a viable means of earning a living, provided one has a genuine passion for it and is willing to promote their work. Does it have the potential to combat poverty and unemployment?" Many

participants saw content creation as a viable means of earning a living, either directly through monetisation or indirectly through opportunities and partnerships. In line with the UGT, participants' pursuit of empowerment and financial gain through content creation reflected their active selection of media to fulfil financial goals, aligning with the theory's assumption that "media use is perceived to be goal-directed" (Blumler & Katz, 1974). Many participants believed content creation can economically empower individuals, especially the youth, to combat poverty and unemployment. This is supported by Nwankwor et al. (2024), who found that social media content creation provides self-employment opportunities and enables youths to earn a living through online entrepreneurship. Ultimately, the potential of content creation to economically empower individuals, especially the youth, is a promising solution to combat poverty and unemployment, and its exploration and development should be prioritised.

Theme 2: Platform dynamics

1.10.5 Participants were asked to describe their frequency and consistency in content creation, including challenges they faced in maintaining a posting schedule.

Sub-theme 2.1: Frequency and consistency

In essence, consistency is about reliability, while frequency is about volume, and content creators can be consistent without being frequent, and vice versa. Many participants mentioned posting content daily or regularly (Participants 1, 2, 7, 8, and 9). As Participant 8 noted, "I post daily vlogs about my day, including classes, shopping, and netball practice." Moreover, consistency was a significant challenge for some participants, who struggled with time constraints, lack of content, and difficulty in maintaining a consistent posting schedule (Participants 4, 5, 6, and 7). Participant 8 stated, "I'm not a full-time content creator because it's overwhelming. People think it's easy, but creating content requires time, passion, and consistency. I used to quit due to time constraints, as I'm always at school studying, researching, and doing assignments." The study found that several participants, a significant portion of whom are full-time content creators, exhibited varying levels of frequency and consistency in posting content, with some posting daily or regularly, while others, some part-time content creators, struggled with maintaining consistency due to time constraints and running out of content. This is supported by Hersh (2020), who notes that most content creators struggle to be consistent because the intention is there, but they are often too

busy with other things to have enough time or energy left to create content, and as a result, consistency becomes a significant challenge. In line with the UGT, participants posted content daily or regularly to fulfil goals like visibility and audience engagement, reflecting the theory's core assumption that "media use is goal-directed" (Falgoust et al., 2022).

1.10.6 Participants were asked to explain the amount of time they spend on Facebook in their daily life.

Sub-theme 2.2: Frequency and duration of use

Frequency and duration of use on Facebook refer to how often users access the platform and how long they spend using it, respectively. Participants reported varying levels of Facebook usage, ranging from less than an hour (Participant 7) to over 10 hours (Participant 1) per day. Participant 1 stated, "I post on Facebook daily, typically more than three times a day. According to Facebook analytics, I spend around 10 hours per day on the platform." Some participants used Facebook intermittently throughout the day (Participants 2, 3, and 8), while others spent extended periods on the platform (Participants 1, 4, and 9). Participant 2 noted, "My posting schedule on Facebook varies depending on the content I have. I can post at any time of day – morning, afternoon, or evening." The study found that participants' Facebook usage varied significantly, with some using it intermittently throughout the day, while others spent extended periods, ranging from less than an hour to over 10 hours per day. In line with the UGT, participants' Facebook use reflects their active selection of media to fulfil specific goals, aligning with the theory's assumption that "media use is perceived to be goal-directed" (Blumler & Katz, 1974). This is supported by the varied duration of Facebook usage, which ranged from less than one hour to more than 10 hours per day. These findings contradict those of Howarth (2025), who found that Americans spend an average of 31 minutes per day on Facebook, suggesting that young people exhibit diverse patterns of Facebook usage.

1.10.7 Participants were required to explain how they perceived the role of Facebook in facilitating their involvement in content creation.

Sub-theme 2.3: Facebook as a platform for content sharing

Facebook, as a platform for content sharing, refers to the relationship between Facebook and content creation, highlighting how Facebook enables and facilitates the creation, dissemination, and interaction with various types of content. All participants emphasised Facebook's importance as a platform for sharing content, reaching a large audience, and building a community (Participants 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10). "Facebook provides content creators with a platform to showcase their talent, and in return, content creators contribute to Facebook's growth. This symbiotic relationship is a win-win for both parties," noted Participant 3. This symbiotic relationship between Facebook and content creation underscores Facebook's role in enabling content creators to showcase their talent and build a community. In line with the UGT, participants' active use of Facebook for content sharing reflects their goal-directed media use, aligning with the theory's assumption that "media use is perceived to be goal-directed" (Blumler & Katz, 1974). The study found that participants viewed Facebook as a platform for content creators, highlighting a symbiotic relationship between Facebook and content creation. This was confirmed by Fu et al. (2017) in Taiwan, who found that Facebook serves as a prominent platform for content sharing, with users sharing a vast amount of diverse content. This means that Facebook serves as a platform for content creation among young people.

Sub-theme 2.4: Account type and verification

There are three common Facebook account types: Standard Account, Professional Mode Account, and Facebook Page, typically used for businesses and public figures. Verification, denoted by a verification badge, confirms the authenticity of an account, indicating that the owner is genuine and legitimate. Only Participant 4 had a verified account, obtained by paying for verification, stating "I paid for verification to prove my account's authenticity", while the remaining participants had unverified accounts due to various reasons, such as a lack of money or not liking the monthly fees, with Participant 7 noting "If you need verification, you have to pay for it". The study found that most participants used Professional Mode accounts, citing benefits like convenient features and analytics, a few used Standard Accounts, a few used Facebook Pages, and only one had a verified account. In line with the UGT, participants' preference for Professional Mode accounts reflects their active selection of media to fulfil specific goals, such as accessing analytics and features, aligning with the theory's assumption that "media use is perceived to be goal-directed" (Blumler &

Katz, 1974). This finding highlights the growing involvement of youth in the content creation industry, where Professional Mode accounts offer valuable tools and features for showcasing their work, connecting with audiences, and monetising their content, contradicting the literature that suggests that most Facebook users use personal profiles (Meta, 2025).

Theme 3: Challenge

1.10.8 The researcher wanted to know the challenges and barriers faced by the content creators and how they overcome them.

Sub-theme 3.1: Technical challenges

Technical challenges in content creation refer to obstacles such as network issues, data limitations, inadequate equipment, and a lack of editing skills that hinder the production, posting, and dissemination of high-quality content. Participants mentioned facing technical challenges such as network issues, data limitations, and inadequate equipment (Participants 1, 3, 4, 7, 8, 9, and 10). Participant 1 stated, "Network problems often hinder my ability to post content, resulting in fewer uploads than intended," while Participant 3 added, "As a content creator, I need data to reach my audience, but it's expensive, and I'm not generating any income." Participants overcame these challenges by using multiple SIM cards, creating backup accounts, deleting old videos to free up space, relying on donations, and learning new skills through apps like Canva. In line with the UGT, participants actively used content creation to fulfil financial goals, aligning with the theory's assumption that "media use is perceived to be goal-directed" (Blumler & Katz, 1974). The study found that technical challenges are a significant obstacle for content creators, hindering their ability to produce and disseminate high-quality content. This is supported by Nwankwor et al. (2024), who found that technical challenges, specifically inadequate networks, hinder content creation. Technical challenges like network issues, data limitations, and inadequate equipment are major obstacles for youth in the Capricorn district involved in content creation. Interventions like installing free Wi-Fi hotspots, providing equipment, and digital skills training could unlock opportunities for them to monetise their content on platforms like Facebook, helping address poverty and unemployment.

1.11 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSION

1.11.1 Summary of key findings

Theme 1: Economic empowerment

The study sought to find the role of Facebook content creation in economically empowering the youth in the Capricorn district, focusing on monetisation, career opportunities, and poverty alleviation. The findings revealed that while content creation is a viable means of economic empowerment, participants faced challenges in maintaining consistency and overcoming technical issues such as network problems and inadequate equipment.

Theme 2: Platform dynamics

The study sought to explore the platform dynamics of Facebook content creation among the youth in the Capricorn district, focusing on frequency and consistency, duration of use, Facebook as a platform for content sharing, and account type and verification. The findings revealed that while Facebook is a crucial platform for content creation, consistency is a significant challenge, with some participants struggling to maintain a consistent posting schedule due to time constraints and running out of content.

Theme 3: Challenges

The study sought to explore the challenges and barriers faced by content creators in the Capricorn district, focusing on technical obstacles and how they overcame these challenges to producing and disseminating high-quality content. The findings revealed that technical challenges, including network issues, data limitations, and inadequate equipment, significantly obstructed the production and dissemination of high-quality content, hindering content creators' ability to effectively create and share content.

1.11.2 Recommendations of the study

The study found that Facebook content creation has the potential to economically empower youth in the Capricorn district, offering opportunities for monetisation, career advancement, and poverty alleviation. However, its effectiveness is hindered by challenges such as inconsistency in posting due to time constraints and a lack of content, network issues, data limitations, inadequate equipment, and limited access

to verification and Professional Mode accounts. With the right support and infrastructure, such as access to quality equipment, data, and digital skills training, Facebook content creation can be a viable strategy for addressing youth unemployment and poverty in rural areas. Therefore, this study recommends that the Capricorn District Municipality install free Wi-Fi hotspots in its communities to provide young content creators with reliable internet access. Furthermore, the NYDA should offer funding, equipment, and digital skills training to support talented content creators who lack resources, enabling them to unlock their potential and create employment opportunities through social media content creation.

1.11.3 Recommendation for future study

Since the study found that Facebook content creation presents a promising entrepreneurial opportunity for youth in the Capricorn district to overcome poverty and unemployment, the researcher recommends that media scholars investigate the role of social media entrepreneurship in the creator economy as a strategy to address youth unemployment in post-COVID-19 South Africa, aligning with Agenda 2030's goals to promote economic participation, entrepreneurship, and job creation among young people, and supporting the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals.

1.11.4 Limitations of the study

The study proposed or targeted content creators with Facebook-verified accounts and a minimum of 10,000 followers. However, the researcher managed to find only six participants with 10,000+ followers, while the other four had around 5,000 followers. Only one participant, with 5,800 followers, had a verified account. This occurred due to difficulties in finding targeted participants in the area, some participants withdrawing during the interviews, and others declined the invitation to participate. Lastly, the first and third objectives were of a quantitative nature, so the study would have been more effective if it employed mixed methods and answered the two objectives through survey questionnaires. However, these limitations did not affect the quality of the study, as essential and relevant information was provided.

1.12 CONCLUSION

Facebook content creation enables users to produce and share engaging video content, achieving personal and business goals, such as building brand awareness,

monetising content, and earning a living. According to Bhargava (2022), content creators are digitally savvy, creative individuals who produce content around their interests, hobbies, and experiences, distributing and monetising it on digital platforms. The study found that the proliferation of Facebook content creation has economically empowered the youth in the rural Capricorn district, unlocking opportunities for personal and economic growth in a traditionally underserved area. As digitally savvy and creative individuals, these young content creators leverage Facebook to build brand awareness, monetise their content, and earn a living. Despite facing challenges, this study demonstrated that the youth in the rural Capricorn district are actively involved in content creation, driven by motivations beyond monetary benefits. Guided by the UGT, which underpinned the study, the findings highlight the importance of understanding the complex factors driving the behaviours and intentions of these young content creators. As the job market evolves, with social media and artificial intelligence becoming central hubs for employment, youth in the rural Capricorn district must seize content creation opportunities. Monetisation of their Facebook accounts and digital skill development can prepare them for a future with scarce traditional employment opportunities. Ultimately, this study concluded that Facebook content creation presents a viable pathway for economic empowerment among youth in the rural Capricorn district. The Capricorn District Municipality and NYDA are urged to provide support and resources to foster the growth and development of this emerging industry.

1.13 DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this research are available from the author, Baburi N.A, upon reasonable request.

1.14 CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Authors declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

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